

Paper 11

**AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF INTERPERSONAL
STYLES WITH SPECIFIC REFERENCE TO
EMPLOYEES IN SERVICE SECTOR**

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ABSTRACT

An empirical study of Interpersonal Styles with specific reference to employees in service sector is to find out the interpersonal styles and Ego states of the employees who work in service sector. We used primary data to our study; the primary data was collected from 100 samples from employees of Hinduja Global Solutions Mangalore. For collection of information we prepared a well questionnaire about interpersonal styles of employees. We made our survey on the basis of random selection so we selected samples from male and female respondents randomly. Well questionnaire was prepared with the faculty guide. After the observation of our study we came know that many employees are ego states and interpersonal styles will come to picture when they usually not want to do the things that they do not like.

Key Words: Interpersonal Styles, Ego States

Introduction:

Usually in an organization inter personal styles (more over skills) of an employees will differ from one person to another. Interpersonal Styles includes Ego States, Personality, Attitude, Perception, Emotions, Behaviour, Skills, Ethics, Intelligence etc., each person has his own habits that are unique from one person to another and the way of perceiving the world and interacting with it.

Inter Personal Styles can be defined as the life skills that are used every day to communicate and interact with other people, both individually and in groups. It is a combination of responses to internal and external stimulis or the concrete of action engaged in by a person. Understanding of interpersonal styles (skills) in an essential tool to help us to understand the way people behave and how they perhaps and interact with each other.

The Interpersonal Styles of employees is influenced by various factors like culture, values, attitudes, ethics, hypnosis, genetics, emotions, persuasion, and authority. Some of the styles

are common, some unusual, some acceptable and some outside acceptable limits. Some of the factors lie with himself, e.g., his instincts, personality traits, internal feelings, etc., while some factors lie outside him comprising the external environments of which he is a part, e.g., weather conditions, events conveying some information and other people's behavior that directly influences is styles (skills). People who have worked on developing strong interpersonal styles are usually more successful in both their personal lives and professional.

Some of the Interpersonal Styles:

1. Interaction with Subordinates or Superior
2. Interaction in relation to values and norms
3. Interaction With affection, fear, anger, curiosity
4. Ego states like Nurturing parents, Controlling parents, Creative parents, Adoptive parents, Rebellious child
5. Supportive & Aggressive individual style

Literature Review:

Interpersonal style is mainly based on behavioural perspective of individual to understand the predominant styles what he/she has. Factors like Transactional analysis, Ego states with different interpersonal styles (Supportive, Rescuing, Normative, Prescriptive) interpersonal Styles is optimized which will lead to organizational effectiveness. (Dr.Arindam Chatterjee)

There are four distinctive interpersonal styles all are made up with components like Director, Expressive, Relater and Thinker. Styles are influenced by whether the person is open in their responsiveness or controlled to how much information he reveals, and how he/she shares his/her feelings and emotions. (Jen Jones)

Interpersonal Styles are the Ability to Motivate, Communicate, and Build Team and its effectiveness at different levels of Management. These skills are important for effective leadership and organisational change. (Aamir Khan & Dr.Wisal Ahmad)

"If you don't care what the person is saying don't pretend you do. They always know. If the timing is off for a conversation or you aren't interested at all, tell them. They may be upset but they will be more upset if they try to talk to you and realize you don't care."(Linda Finkle)

Effective interpersonal interactions involve caring, to establish cooperation, and at the same time directness, to communicate in an unambiguous way. The ability to perform these tasks varies with personality and the importance of these tasks varies across jobs. (Lex Borghans, Bruce A. Weinberg, 2006)

Constructivism focuses on attempting to explain individuals' differences in communicating skilfully (Griffin, 2009).

According to Garavan, Thomes N in his study titled "Interpersonal skills training for quality interaction" Today in each individual's employee behaviour in organization is different from one to another. The Garavan Thomes N is discussing about the quality of services providing in Tourism and hospitality sector .This study focuses on the human resource dimension by

providing quality of training and development activities to each employee it will make them to more skilled employees.

Interpersonal skills can be defined broadly as “those skills which one needs in order to communicate effectively with another person or a group of people” (Rungapadiachy, 1999, p.193).

Strong interpersonal skills protect against depression in youth. Depressed youth demonstrate weaker interpersonal skills (O’Shea et al. 2013).

The ability to listen effectively is a core skill in a range of interpersonal situations (Bostrom, 1997).

The ability to use questions that maximise the amount of relevant (relative to irrelevant) information that is gathered in an exchange, serves to enhance the communicative efficiency of the interaction of Interpersonal skills (Hayes, 2002).

Being effective at helping others is considered an important aspect of interpersonal competence (Hayes, 2002; Rungapadiachy, 1999).

A popular method for identifying ego states is the Ego gram which presents an individual’s ego state energy distribution in the form of bar charts of five ego state functions (Nurturing Parent, Critical Parent, Adult, Free Child and Adapted Child). (Dusay, 1972).

Thorne & Faro (1980) suggest that earlier attempts to measure ego states in a systematic and quantifiable manner were fraught with methodological problems (e.g. deviation from accepted TA concepts, limited samples, and insufficient evidence of validity).

Berne’s asserted that ego states are directly observable phenomena rather than abstract theoretical constructs (Stewart, 2010).

Berne defined the Child ego state as ‘a set of feelings, attitudes and behaviors which are relics of an individual’s own childhood’ (Berne, 1961: 69).

Supportive interpersonal style is refers to support is provided when needed. James (Pareek, 2002).

Sulking interpersonal style means People with this style keep their negative feelings to themselves, find it difficult to share them. (Dr. Arindam Chatterjee).

Normative interpersonal style means employees are interested in developing proper norms of behaviours for their subordinates. (Dr. Arindam Chatterjee).

Aggressive interpersonal styles means how people with their style are fighters. They may fight for their subordinates, clients of participants or for their ideas and suggestions, hoping that this will help them achieve desired results. (Dr. Arindam Chatterjee).

Objectives of the Study:

- 1. To understand the Interpersonal styles of each employees in organisation
- 2. To study the ego states of the employees
- 3. To know the different behaviour of employees in different vocations
- 4. How Interpersonal Styles affects employees working environment

Research Methodology:

An empirical study of Interpersonal Styles with specific reference to employees in service sector. This research is based on survey method. The present study is confined to Mangalore area. We are selected Hinduja Global Solution (HGS) Ltd Mangalore as our research place. On the basis of probability sampling under that we selected simple random sampling to measure the samples and we used primary data to our study. It is decided that out whole employee’s population we will consider only 100 as our research samples. The Questionnaire consist of 36 questions and we used Liker’s scale to measure the samples.

Result and Discussion:

Table 1: No of Respondent

Gender	Respondent
Male	42
Female	58

From the above graph depicts that, majority of the respondents are female respondents and in that 42 are male, 58 are female respondents so total we found in our study is 100 respondents.

Table 2: Age Group of Respondent

Age Group	Respondent
18-25	80
25-35	20
35-45	0
45&Above	0

The table showing whole as 100 respondents in we found 80% are fallen in the age between 18-25 year and 20% are fallen in 25-35 year age groups. In our respondents we didn't found any respondents are which belongs to age group between 35-45 and 45&above.

Table 3: Education Qualification:

Qualification	Respondent
PG	3
UG	53
PUC	44

From the whole respondents we found majority respondents are under graduate people who responded our questionnaire and 44 respondents are PUC holders and minority respondents are UG holders I.e.,3.

Table 4: I Delay Doing Things That I Do Not Like

Scale	Respondent
Never behave this way	7
Occasionally behave this way	51
Sometimes behave this way	26
Often behave this way	8
Always behave this way	8

From the above chart it is clear that majority of respondents are went for occasionally behave this way for delay doing things that they do not like and rest of 26 respondents are sometimes

they behave when they delay their work, least respondents are saying they often, always and never behave this way for delaying their work that they do not like.

Table 5: Encourage my colleagues to discuss with me about what should or should not be done

Never behave this way	13
Occasionally behave this way	23
Sometimes behave this way	37
Often behave this way	12
Always behave this way	15

From the above chart it is clear that encouraging their colleagues while working majority are saying they sometimes behave and occasionally are doing 23 respondents, least respondents are saying that they often behave when it is comes to an encouraging their colleagues while working.

Table 6: I admonish my staff for not acting according to my instructions

Never behave this way	19
Occasionally behave this way	29
Sometimes behave this way	23
Often behave this way	8
Always behave this way	21

From the above chart majority of respondents are occasionally behave when it comes to admonish of their staff for not acting according to the instructions, sometimes people responds same as they responded for occasional and least respondents are saying they often behave when it comes to their staff are not acting as per the instructions.

Table 7: I collect information and data even when these are not immediately needed or used.

Never behave this way	10
Occasionally behave this way	35
Sometimes behave this way	29
Often behave this way	7
Always behave this way	19

From the above chart it is clear that majority respondents are occasionally behave when it comes to their work related information and data collection which is immediately needed or

used, so 29 respondents are sometimes do and least people are saying they often behave when the information and data which is required immediately.

Table 8: I avoid meeting my seniors and staff if I have not been able to fulfil their expectations.

Never behave this way	12
Occasionally behave this way	37
Sometimes behave this way	30
Often behave this way	6
Always behave this way	15

From the above chart it is clear majority respondents are saying they do occasionally behave when it comes to meet their senior staff if not able to fulfil the expectations and rest 30 respondents are saying they do sometimes behave and least are saying often they behave when it is to meet their senior staff.

Table 9: I accept other’s suggestions that appeal to me.

Never behave this way	6
Occasionally behave this way	21
Sometimes behave this way	23
Often behave this way	15
Always behave this way	35

From the above chart it is clear that when people accept others suggestions they do appeal and majority respondents are saying they always behave while accepting others suggestions, rest few respondents are went for occasional, sometimes and often and least respondents are went for never behave while accepting others suggestions.

Table 10: I zealously agree my point of view in organisational meetings

Never behave this way	3
Occasionally behave this way	43
Sometimes behave this way	28
Often behave this way	13
Always behave this way	13

From the above chart it clear that majority respondents are occasionally behave when it is come to zealously agree point of view in the organisational meetings and rest are neutrally saying sometimes, often and almost but least respondents are saying they rarely behave their argue in the organisational meetings.

Table 11: I accept help from others and appreciate it

Never behave this way	7
Occasionally behave this way	34
Sometimes behave this way	19
Often behave this way	18
Always behave this way	22

From the above chart it is clear that majority of respondents are saying they occasionally behave when they accept help from others and appreciate it, rest are neutral by saying sometimes, always and often and least respondents are saying they never behave when it is to accept help from others and appreciate it.

Table 12: I clearly prescribed standards of behaviour to be followed in my work unit.

Never behave this way	4
Occasionally behave this way	37
Sometimes behave this way	26
Often behave this way	14
Always behave this way	19

From the above chart it is clear that majority of respondents are saying occasionally behave when they clearly prescribe standard of behaviour to be followed in the work unit, rest few are saying sometimes, often and always behaves and least respondents are saying they are never behave this way when the standards to be followed in the work unit.

Table13: While working on organisational tasks, I do not give much importance to the feeling of people.

Never behave this way	5
Occasionally behave this way	15
Sometimes behave this way	20
Often behave this way	12
Always behave this way	48

From the above graph it is clear that majority of the respondents are saying they always behave when it is give importance to the feeling of the people and rest of the respondents are showing neutral response to occasionally, sometimes and often behave and least of respondents are saying never behave when it is comes to show their feelings of people.

Table14: Statements

Questions	If you rarely or never behave this way	If you occasionally behave this way	If you sometimes behave this way	If you often behave this way	If you almost always behave this way
Q1. I assure my people of my availability to them	47	18	6	6	23
Q2. I communicate strong feelings and resentment to my colleagues/seniors without caring whether this will affect my relationship with them	6	31	12	23	28
Q3. I collect all the information needed to solve various problems	42	20	20	2	26
Q4. I discuss with my people new ideas that occur to me, without working out their details.	4	50	20	2	16
	If you rarely or never behave this way	If you occasionally behave this way	If you sometimes behave this way	If you often behave this way	If you almost always behave

	way				this way
Q5. I respect and follow those traditions of the organization that seem to give it its identity.	21	24	29	12	14
Q6. I provide my staff with solutions to their problems	9	34	20	14	21
Q7. I take up the causes of my department/people and fight for them.	19	29	23	8	21
Q8. I think of new and creative solutions.	10	41	16	12	21
Q9. I help my people to become aware of some of their own strengths.	12	37	30	6	15
Q10. I help my people to see the ethical dimensions of some of their actions.	6	40	24	10	20
Q11. While I champion my subordinate's cause, organizational considerations have low priority for me.	8	36	26	13	17
Q12. I think out many alternative solutions to a problem before adopting one for action.	4	37	26	9	24
Q13. I overwhelm my colleagues with new ideas	12	26	34	14	14
Q14. I instruct my people in detail about work problems and their solutions.	36	26	17	8	16
Q15. I give clear instructions to my people about what should or should not be done.	14	28	33	9	16
Q16. I try out new things.	5	28	23	25	19
Q17. I go with my people into all the details of the specific work at hand.	11	30	22	10	27
Q18. I reassure my people of my continual help	8	35	21	16	20

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MANEGMA-2017

ISBN No: 978-93-5268-756-5

Q19. I continue to be bothered by the negative feelings which I am not able to express during unpleasant meetings	10	31	30	11	18
	If you rarely or never behave this way	If you occasionally behave this way	If you sometimes behave this way	If you often behave this way	If you almost always behave this way
Q20. I help my colleagues and the staff to examine the appropriateness of proposed actions	4	47	23	11	15
Q21. I express strong resentment to the authorities concerned about things that have not been as promised	16	34	19	10	21
Q22. I continuously search various resources from which needed information can be obtained in order to work out solutions to problems.	10	38	27	10	15
Q23. Even if earlier ideas or methods have not been consolidated, I try out new ones I come across	8	32	37	6	17
Q24. I encourage my people to come to me frequently for my advice and help	4	42	20	14	20
Q25. I express my feelings and reactions frankly in meetings with my seniors and colleagues	2	34	29	19	16
Q26. I enjoy trying out new ways and see a problem as a challenge	2	22	30	24	22

Total Respondents of the table:

Never behave this way	297
Occasionally behave this way	926
Sometimes behave this way	643
Often behave this way	334
Always behave this way	500

For the rest of questions we framed in the questionnaire respondents are showing their different ego and interpersonal behaviour and we found majority of the respondents i.e., 34% of the respondents are saying they occasionally behave while showing their interpersonal styles, 24% of the respondents are saying sometimes behave, 19% are always behave, 12% are oftenly behave and least respondents are saying they never behave when they show their ego and interpersonal styles in an organization.

Findings and Suggestions:

After the observation of our research we found that most of employees of HGS are showing their moderate response towards their ego and interpersonal style and other work related aspects. From our survey we found that 51 responds are sometimes delay their work 27 respondents are sometimes delay their work that they do not like so rest all saying they delay when they do not like. While encouraging people majority 37 respondents are sometimes encourage their colleagues and 23 respondents are occasionally behave to their colleagues to discuss about what should done or should not. The employees are occasionally and rarely or never behaving is preferred in most of our questions. 29 respondents are preferred occasionally when it comes to admonish staff for not acting according to his/her instructions. When collecting information matter comes 35 respondents are occasionally collect information when it is immediately used. 35 respondents are accept others suggestions while any kind of help is required. 43 respondents are zealously argue point of view in meeting and 28 respondents are sometimes behaves. 34 respondents are occasionally behaved when it comes accept help from others and appreciate it. 48 respondents are giving very good importance when it comes to the feelings of the people.

By considering all the above findings we suggest that employees in service sector should be cooperated with their colleagues so that they can express their feelings and standard of

behaviour followed in a work place and accept thing from others and appreciate it, ego states should be avoided during working with their colleagues. Employees should accept others suggestions that appeal to every employees, respect and follow those tradition of organisation that seems to its identity and have assure of availability to the organization.

Conclusion:

The study has been clearly stating that the employees are showing different behaviors in different vocations and styles also they have ego states. This study have also found some problems which occur due to some behavioral aspects and also given some suggestion that can be help them to overcome from those problems. Interpersonal styles and ego states of employees are more differ from one person to another in an organization. As we stated in our objective that how interpersonal styles affects employees working environment it is proved in our study that some occasion employees are hesitating to express their feelings in the meeting and with their senior staffs, ego is the one of problem to delay the work given to them that employees do not like, while encouraging colleagues, admonishing staff for not acting according to the instructions, so these kinds of ego will be a problem will be a big problem while working in an organization along with colleagues. Interpersonal styles mainly positive manner to motivate, communicate and in team building with colleagues and as per our study it is clear that interpersonal styles will effects his work environment and each employees will have different interpersonal styles in an organization. Employee's show their own interpersonal styles and egos in different vocation when any kind of work is assigned to them that they do not like do.

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